

Research

Impact of Human Resource Practices on Perceived Performance: A Case of Afghanistan

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Abstract: This paper analyzed the effect of the most common practices of human resource management including performance evaluation, compensation, and promotion. These human resource practices are used as independent variable, whereas perceived performance is employed as dependent variable. For accomplishment of research objective, the teaching faculty of six prominent private universities of Nangarhar is deployed. The response was taken from 123 respondents, and findings indicated a significant positive relationship between human resource practices: compensation, performance evaluation, and promotion practices and perceived performance of teachers in private universities of Nangarhar province, Afghanistan. Future implications were given to the human resource management practices, universities administration, and the rest of the educational sectors of Afghanistan.

Keywords: Compensation, Human Resource Practices, Promotion, Performance Evaluation, Nangarhar, Afghanistan.

Introduction

The Human resource management is based on the deliberate and systematic technique, used in organization management by appraising workers for their efforts in fulfilling the objectives of that organization. HRM considered them as a precious asset of the organization (Armstrong, 1995). Many researches have been done on the effect of HRM practices on the organization, and

employee work performances and most of them reflected a notable effect of HRM on the employee and organization performance (Becker & Huselid, 1998). According to the different researchers, human resources management has shown a significantly relationship with worker's performance (Gould-Williams, 2003; Teclemichael Tessema & Soeters, 2006). The organizational performance was also found to be strongly associated with HRM practices (Cures et al. 2010). These practices are known as essential tool to increase the productivity of the organization and the efficiency of an employee. This tool is essential to secure a combative place in the business sector (Pfeffer, 1994; Schuler & MacMillan, 1984).

There are different researched based studies have been conducted for the wellbeing of the human resource practices and their worker's work performance, but the majority of them restricted their researchers to the developed states (Aycan et al., 2000). There are very few studies conducting in under-developing countries like India, Pakistan and particular to Afghanistan. One of the few researchers has been done in Pakistan by Shahzad et al. (2008). The study concluded that HR practices were limited to government universities only, but besides this, a strong relationship was found between the performances of employees and HR activities. Due to the lack of adequate resources and lousy performance of teachers in the educational sector, the literacy rate in Pakistan is considerably low (Shahzad et al., 2008). Afghanistan as a developing country, was named as an (under-researched) state by (Aycan et al., 2000). The study also points out that some of the public organizations in Afghanistan still not developed HRM setups properly. On the contrary, private organizations embracing this system very rapidly. The human resource system plays a significant role in the success of the organization. It refers to managing all the decisions within an organization that will create a relationship between workers and organization. The actual purpose of establishing HR practices setups in private organizations is to keep check and balance on the employee performance, trained them according to their capacities and organizational needs, hire new employees or fire anyone in case of not meeting the regulatory standards. In this way, the organization can meet the competitive position in the market.

The present paper comes up with an overview of the human resource management system in private universities of Nangarhar. Nangarhar is an under-developed province of Afghanistan which has severely damaged by terrorist attacks.

The private universities in Nangarhar are not well established in terms of HRM setup, and there is a need to research on the activities of human resource management and university's teaching

faculty performances. This paper contributes to research by focusing "Impact of human resource practices on the perceived employee performance in private universities of the Nangarhar".

Statement of the Problem

Various studies that have done in underdeveloped have not mentioned any significant relation among HR practice and work performance. But from the theoretical perspective, there seems a connection between these two aspects. Employees who perceive increments, appraisals, or promotions and performance evaluation sufficient are probably more focused on their work. They will provide adequate efforts to the organization. On the other hand, the employee who sees promotion, compensation, and performance evaluation insufficient, they will stop putting efforts to their work. These two different attitudes of employee performance show how human resource management practices influenced the work performance of the organizational workers.

There is a huge impact on the performance of employee by the human resource management and it is a great topic for research. However, most of the studies conducted on it were limited to developed countries only. In Afghanistan, particularly in Nangarhar, microscopic researches can be seen in this context. Unit of time practice shows that from developed countries to developing countries study, it has a considerable impact on organizational performance. This study provides an argument based on the current database unit of time practices in under developing states. It will be evaluated by the mutual understanding of the human resource department and the performance sheet of the professors.

Research Question

“What is the effect of human resource management practices on the perceived work performance of teachers in private sector universities of Nangarhar”?

Literature Review

Human Resource Management Practices

Human resource management practices consisted of performance-based increments, promotions, work training of the employees, development of the organization, labour relationships, or HR planning. These activities play a role as a bridge between strategies and organizational policies (Dessler, 2007). From the literature review, it can be seen that the most common practices that

were focused by the researchers were training (Noe et al., 2007), staff management. (“Becker, 2001; Frye, 2004) observed that compensation was the most common practice that many of the researchers have seen. It has always connected to the employee work performance. In another study conducted by Marwat et al. (2010), “the relationship between Human resource management practices and employee work performance was analyzed with seven methods of human resources”. The results showed a significant correlation between all seven practices and employee performance. Those practices were the selection of employee, training, and increments on performance, career planning, compensation, effective employee participation, and clear job description. Similarly, another study was conducted in which eight practices were used to study their relationship with employee work performance Teclemichael Teseema and Soeters (2006). The current study critically analyzes the three most common practices of human resources like promotion, compensation, and performance evaluation based on the assumption that these are the variables used to enhance employee morale to put their efforts in their assigned work role.

Employee Performance

Aguinis (2009), explained employee performance as to how an employee behaves. According to McCloy et al., (1994), employee performance depends on his behaviour, not on the work he produced. The victory of any organization based on perceived performance that comes from what an employee puts up to his Behavior. He also emphasized three major factors that helped to enhance performance, and these include imperative knowledge, motivation, and procedural knowledge. Employee performance is also defined as a set of values of employee behaviours that he used to put his contributions in achieving organizational objectives (Borman & Motowidlo, 1993; Canmpbell, 1990).

Compensation

Financial honor or non-financial appreciation are considered as the best rewards which anyone can receive. Most of the organizations used these practices to motivate their employee. They become more focused on their goal and try to fulfill them with high morale. It will not only increase employee performance but also mark a great impact on the productivity of the organization (Altarawmneh & Al- Kilani, 2010). Financial rewards that are given based on performance contributes a lot in stimulating employee, to work harder because it is a well-

known fact that money is everyone's priority and need. So, when the employee works tirelessly, his/her performance will be enhanced, and chances of compensation in the future also increased (Lazear, 1999). Another study was conducted by Frye (2004) in which he investigated the relationship between employee performance and compensation. He documented that a positive relation was found between them. In other research, the same relationship was tested, and it was also found that compensation has positively correlated with employee performance (Ahmad & Shahzad, 2011). A study analyzed the correlation between compensation and perceive work performance of university teaching faculty and found a positive association. The staff of the university stated that a handsome package in compensation practice could easily mould a teacher's work performance.

From the above literature review and the fact that employee who got fair compensation, worked with more efficiency, we can be hypostasized that "compensation is positively associated with employee work performance."

H1: There is a positive relationship between compensation and perceived the work performance of teachers in private universities of Nangarhar.

Performance Evaluation Practices

This practice of performance evaluation used to monitor employee performance regularly, and it can help in improving employee performance and work productivity. Brown and Heywood (2005) stated that this practice found very useful to produce loyal employees within the organization, and they become committed to organizational goals. Ruwan (2007), believed that bonus payments, appreciation in front of other employees (motivate others as well to perform better next time), and evaluation of performance plays a very effective role. He names it as "operations by growing competence,"

Better performance from an employee makes a bond of organization and employee in the workspace (Huselid, 1995). A weak relationship found between perceived work performance and performance evaluation. The reason was a lack of performance-based appraisal, which leads employees towards poor performance, and he/she failed to give desirable results to the organization (Shahzad et al., 2008). Ahmad and Shahzad (2011) measured PE with employee performance and concluded the results, which showed an insignificant correlation between them.

In a study, Spearman' Correlation was used, and it showed a significant positive correlation between human resources practices and perceived work performance. Regression analysis was carried out which indicates a significant relation of performance evaluation and employee work performance (“Bowra, Sharif, Saeed & Niazi, 2011; Hashim, 2014; Hashim, Khattak & Kee, 2017”). Banking sectors will be found this research very helpful in upgrading their policies regarding employee performances.

Based on the above arguments that "there is a positive association among perceiving work performance of employee and performance evaluation", we can hypothesize the second hypothesis to measure the relationship of university's teaching faculty performance with performance evaluation practice in private universities of Nangarhar.

H2: There is a positive relationship between performance evaluation and perceived the performance of teachers in private universities of Nangarhar.

Promotion Practices

Promotion practice plays a significant role in individuals' work performance (Guest, 2002). Study conducted by Shahzad et al. (2008) showed a positive connection between promotion practice and employee work performance. They claimed that promotion practice could not only make teachers capable of getting promoted in the hierarchical system of organization, but also give a chance to "serve as a role model in professional development." The majority of studies found a significant relation of promotion practice with employee work performance. Still, Ahmad and Shahzad (2011), research revealed an extremely weak relation of the promotional strategies of the universities.

H3: There is a positive relationship between promotion practice and perceived the work performance of teachers in private universities of Nangarhar.

Methodology

This chapter highlights the process which is carried by the researcher to proceed the process of data collection, targeted population, sample size, statistical data.

Tools of data collection

A self-administrated questionnaire based on the impact of human resource practices on perceived work performance taken from the prior research conducted by Shahzad et al. (2008) was used in

this paper as the variables used in that research were familiar to this present study. Demographic factors always included in any kind of research, so the initial part of the questionnaire consisted of demographic questions with seven items. The 2nd section was about the perceived work performance of the employee (dependent variable). The 3rd section of the questionnaire was based on the items about compensation. There were six questions in that part. The fourth part was about performance evaluation with six questions, and in the last part, three promotion practice questions were asked. Researchers have tested all the measurements and internal consistency. Shahzad et al. (2008) adopted the results of Teclmichael Tessema and Soeters (2006) who tested all the values of alpha within the acceptable region, and all of his values lied within 0.73 - 0.82 range.

According to his data, the value of alpha for compensation practice is 0.82, “for Promotion practice, it is 0.74, for performance evaluation, it is 0.73, and for perceived employee performance it is 0.74”. Five-points Likert scale was used in his study to record the responses. (“One endpoint of Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree and the other endpoint of scale is, 5 = Strongly Agree”).

Target Population

The targeted population for this research consisted 400 respondents from which 200 were male, and 200 were female. They belonged to the private sector universities of Nangarhar. A total of six universities were selected for this research. “These include Al-Taqwa University, Khurasan University, Al-Falah University, Rokhan University, and Spinghar University of Nangarhar.

Sample Size

A convenient sampling was adopted to collect the primary data as teachers was not available all the time. The sample size was taken by using Yamane formula (1967), 136 questionnaires were given in all universities. Twenty respondents were selected as a sample size from each university. Out of 136 questionnaires, 123questionnare were given back, and 13 questionnaires were missed. The percentage of the responses was (89.1%), which was sufficient enough to carry out the analysis.

Statistical Methods

Demographic details are presented in the frequency table (Table1). “Pearson Correlation analysis was used to examine the relationship between independent and dependent variables”.

Figure 1: Research Framework

Table1: Frequency and Percentage of the Demographic

	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	87	70.73
	Female	36	29.26
Age	20-24	15	12.1
	25-29	46	37.3
	30-34	39	31.7
	35-39	15	12.1
	40-44	4	3.2
	45-49	1	1.0
	50 & above	3	2.9
Qualification	Bachelors	6	4.8
	Masters	56	45.5
	MS/M. Phil	50	40.6
	PhD	11	8.9
Marital Status	Married	67	55.3
	Unmarried	56	44.7
Organizational Tenure	0 to 1	40	32.5
	2 to 3	48	36.5
	4 to 5	22	17.8
	6 & above	13	9.4

The reason behind taking these three human resource practices as independent variables was the claim in the study of Shahzad et al. (2008), where he insisted that these activities can become the psychological need of the employee and marked a deep impact on his performance he further stated that teacher's performance may depend on promotion, performance and compensation practices due to the collectivist culture in universities. The study did not examine their relation with performance evaluation. The above table shows the details of the demographics status of the teachers. There were 70.73% male respondents and 29.26% female respondents. The work experience of the majority of teachers was less than 3 years in universities, and more than half percent of the teachers have MS degree holders. Marital status was also an important demographic aspect.

Table 2: Correlation between HR Practices and Teachers' Performance

		Teacher's Performance	Compensation Practice	Performance EV Practice	Promotion Practice
Teacher's Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.470**	.386**	.445**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	123	123	123	123
Compensation Practice	Pearson Correlation	.470**	1	.512**	.645**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	123	123	123	123
Performance Practice	EV Pearson Correlation	.386**	.512**	1	.405**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	123	123	123	123
Promotion Practice	Pearson Correlation	.445**	.645**	.405**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	123	123	123	123

Table 3: Regression Analysis for HR Practices and Teachers' Performance

Model	B	S.E.	β	t	Sig
1					
Constant	2.72	.23	-	11.81	.003*
Compensation Practices	3.33	.17	.18	7.43	.000*
Performance Practices	5.01	.37	.39	10.04	.000*
Promotion Practices	2.02	.23	.53	15.75	.000*
R2= .937					
Durbin Watson=1.708					
Sig F=0.000					

The influence of HR practices on performance of teachers was analyzed by using regression analysis. The outcomes of R indicated that 93.7% change in the performance of teachers through HR practices (compensation practice B= 3.33, β = .180, t =7.43 and p < .001, performance evaluation practices B= 5.01, β = .385, t =10.04 and p < .001, and promotion practices B= 2.02, β = .528, t =15.75 and p < .001). The outcomes as shown in above table HR practices have a positive relationship with teachers' performance".

Data Analysis and Discussion

The SPSS software was used to analyze the data. Pearson correlation analysis and regression analysis were carried out to investigate the relationship of promotion practice, performance evaluation, and compensation practice with the perceived performance of the employee. Responses were taken from 123 respondents to achieve the results.

The result indicated that compensation practice was positively correlated to the perceived performance of teachers with 0.47 value. If compare this value with the outcome of Shahzad et al. (2008), his result was 0.44. So it can be stated that compensation practice has a significant positive impact on the teachers of private universities of Nangarhar. The p-value was also found to be substantial (p<0.5), "which showed that there was a significant relationship between compensation and the perceived performance of the teachers".

The results of performance evaluation practice revealed a positive significant relationship with the perceived performance of teachers with a value of 0.38 and this result was supported by the outcome of Shahzad et al (2008), who found a weak correlation with the value (0.15). The

variation in results show that the private sector regularly used evaluation tools for their teacher's performance. The p-value was also found to be significant ($p < 0.5$), which showed that there was a meaningful relationship between performance evaluation and perceived performance of the teachers.

The promotion is based on the evaluation of the HR department and the performances of teachers with (0.44). Shahzad et al. (2008) found (0.56) value in his results which was supporting the results of the present study. Similarly, the p-value was also found to be significant ($p < 0.5$), which showed that there was a meaningful relationship between promotion practice and perceived performance of the teachers of private universities.

According to the findings of Shahzad et al. (2008), teachers enjoy the promotions as it enhanced their financial status and also the position within the organization. So the current study findings also indicated the same results. So it can be stated that the relationship of promotion practice, performance evaluation, and compensation practice with perceived performance of the employee was found to be positively significant.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to examine the relationship between human resources practiced and the perceived performance of the teachers of private universities in Nangarhar. From the above findings, it is concluded the alliance of promotion practice, performance evaluation, and compensation practice with perceived performance of the teachers in the private universities of Nangarhar was found to be positively significant. The findings were strongly supported by the previous data which was taken through the literature review. From the results, the alternative hypotheses of the present study were accepted (There is a positive relationship between the compensation, performance evaluation, and promotion practices and perceived performance of teachers in private universities of Nangarhar).

The acceptance of alternative hypotheses indicated that if human resource practices adopted by an organization run regularly in universities and keep a strict check on the work performance of teachers, it can be very helpful in enhancing teacher's returns. Teacher's performance can be judged by performance evaluation and be praised through the promotion practices. It will increase the overall performance of universities and leads to success in the future.

Research Implications

This study found a significant positive relation of human resource practices with perceived performance of teachers in universities of Nangarhar. Human resource practices work as an essential tool for enhancing work performance. The findings of the current study confirmed that the teaching faculty is more interested in promotion practices which are subsequent of compensation and performance evaluation.

Like a higher degree status, the promotion of teachers also shows their abilities and intelligence. So it can be assumed that development can be the status of their career achievements.

Some of the future implication needs are observed during this study which are:

- Human resource practices should be a part of every organization (public or private), with great packages of promotion, compensation, and performance evaluation as these practices work as motivational factors that will lead the organization towards increased productivity and a competitive status in the markets.
- Human practices should also be a part of all higher education institutes. This will bring great potential in employee performance.
- More studies are required to conduct on this topic in Nangarhar, mainly so that the city can improve its flaws and share the equal standards of education like the rest of the world.
- In this study, only three practices were examined, in the future, there is a need to investigate more human resource practices. These practices may include training of the staff, selection practices, etc.

Suggestions

- This paper has covered the faculty of private universities of Nangarhar only. In the future, the same research should also be held in public sector universities, so the impact of HR practices can be seen on government employee's performance as well.
- It is based on the private university department in Nangarhar by generalized on all private sector universities, so there is a need to conduct such a study in other provinces of Afghanistan.
- Future studies can also examine “how various dimensions of job performance might be affected by numerous human resource management practices”.

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